

THE IMPACT OF CULTURAL NARRATIVES ON PEACE AND INTEGRITY: AN ANALYSIS OF THE THREE MAJOR CULTURAL SYSTEMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Cultural narratives, including stories, myths, and collective interpretations, shape people's values and belief systems. They provide frameworks for understanding moral behaviour and fostering communal harmony. In Nigerian society, cultural narratives play a crucial role in promoting peace and integrity. Myths and ancestral stories emphasize virtues like honesty, respect, love, diligence, and justice, while also illustrating the consequences of conflict and the dignity in resolving differences. These moral connections foster mutual care, equality, appreciation of differences, and fair resource distribution. Despite their recognition in peace and conflict studies, there is limited understanding of how specific cultural systems can contribute to peace and integrity in a globalizing world. This study examines the role of cultural narratives in enhancing peace among Nigeria's three major cultures. It explores cultural identities, myths, values, traditional beliefs, and social structures. Using a qualitative approach with historical and hermeneutic methods, the study underscores the importance of cultural narratives in promoting peace and development. Findings will demonstrate how cultural narratives encourage reconciliation, cooperation, and equality, which are essential for peaceful coexistence and community well-being.

Keywords: Culture, Cultural Narratives, Ethnic Groups, Tradition, Myths

Introduction

Understanding the concept of cultural narratives will delineate their roles in peacebuilding and integrity within the people that are culturally related. First, a narrative consists of a series of fictional or non-fictional events typically presented chronologically. It is a story constructed in an organized manner, featuring a plot, characters, structure, setting, and theme (Loyola et al, 2023). Narratives serve many purposes beyond mere entertainment and escapism; they are the main means people comprehend and assign significance to their lives. Green (2021) underscores conveying personal thoughts and emotions, crafting cautionary tales about potential consequences of carelessness, developing morality stories that guide us toward being better individuals and preserving the history of human civilization as the purposes of narratives. Given the powerful impact of narratives, it is clear that people can be significantly influenced by shared concepts emerging from fiction. The greater the number of individuals engaged in sharing these stories, the larger the communities they establish. Eventually, the interplay between narratives and their storytellers gives rise to a cultural narrative. Thus, a cultural narrative encompasses a collection of beliefs, ideas, and stories that define a particular society.

Cultural narratives refer to the shared stories, beliefs, and values that a particular group of people holds which shapes its identity, tradition and worldview. These narratives can include myths, folklore, historical accounts and modern representations. They play a significant role on how individuals within a culture understand themselves and their place in the world.

Individuals across the world use cultural narratives to convey their identities and gain self-understanding. This is significant in shaping societal values, beliefs, and behaviours. According to Writer (2015), cultural narratives consist of stories, myths, or shared interpretations that help a culture explain and make sense of the world. These narratives are deeply ingrained in a society's collective mindset and significantly influence behaviour. Cultural narratives offer a framework for determining what is deemed acceptable or unacceptable, right or wrong, and valuable or insignificant within a specific cultural context. While separating cultural narratives from mere ideologies, Benadum (2024) states that cultural narratives shape how individuals perceive their relationships with others. These comprise of self-identity influence, roles in society, and expectations about others. For instance, gender roles are often shaped by these narratives. In cultures where men are seen as the primary providers, men may feel obligated to pursue high-paying careers, while women may be expected to prioritize household duties. Hence, cultural narratives affect people's attitudes toward social issues. Fundamentally, cultural narratives play a vital role in shaping behaviour by providing a lens for understanding the world, influencing people's beliefs and perceptions, and guiding their actions.

In various societies, especially in Africa, cultural narratives go beyond storytelling to represent life experiences that shape social norms and expectations. According to Owosh (2020), storytelling fosters a sense of communal relationships among children. In African culture, an individual's identity is deeply rooted in and recognized through their community. This is because community serves as the foundation and essence of African life. The African concept of security and its significance is tied to personal connection and belonging within the community. This implies that African communities uphold various moral and societal values designed to govern interpersonal relationships and sustain the community as a whole. They adhere to specific standards or norms intended to promote social cohesion and ensure the smooth functioning of the community. These guidelines help prevent individuals from acting rebelliously and threatening the well-being of society.

In Nigeria, the impact of cultural narratives on peace and integrity is multifaceted. Cultural narratives are intricately woven into the social fabric, playing a significant role in influencing peace and integrity. These narratives promote social cohesion and a sense of belonging, fostering a collective identity that transcends individual differences. They also provide a moral framework that encourages respect for others, communal responsibility, and peaceful coexistence as seen in many Nigerian proverbs and folktales which emphasize the importance of unity, empathy, and mutual support and values that are essential for maintaining peace in a diverse society. Hence, cultural narratives are a powerful force in shaping the moral and ethical landscape of Nigerian society. As Nigeria continues to navigate the challenges of modernization and globalization, it is essential to critically examine the role of cultural narratives in promoting or undermining peace and integrity and to explore ways of preserving and revitalizing these narratives in a manner that supports social harmony and cohesion.

This paper therefore explores how cultural narratives within the Nigerian major ethnic groups can influence peace and integrity. By analyzing specific cultural practices and their underlying

narratives, the study seeks to highlight the dual role these narratives can play in both fostering and undermining societal harmony. The study also offers insights into how these narratives can be harnessed or reinterpreted to promote a more inclusive and peaceful Nigerian society. The significance of this study is based on its potential to offer a profound understanding of the cultural dynamics that influence peace and integrity in the three major ethnic groups of Nigeria. By examining the ways in which cultural narratives shape social norms and behaviours, the study shares insights to the development of culturally sensitive approaches to peacebuilding and conflict resolution that are grounded in the values and traditions of Nigerian core ethnic groups.

Statement of the problem

Nigeria is home to over 250 ethnic groups and the largest and most politically influential ethnic groups are the Hausa-Fulani (29%), Yoruba (21%), Igbo (18%), Ijaw (10%), Kanuri (4%), Ibibio (3.5%), and Tiv (2.5%) (Ologunagbe, Olamide (2023)). There are more than 500 dialects spoken within Nigeria, making it the most ethnically and culturally diverse country in Africa (Oluwadele et al., 2023). Each of these ethnic groups has its unique cultural narratives which are often expressed through oral traditions, folklores, proverbs, rituals, and ceremonies, and these play a significant role in shaping the moral and ethical standards of Nigerian society. Nigerian cultural diversity however is both a source of strength and a potential cause of conflict because it enriches the nation with a wealth of traditions and practices that contribute to its unique identity and can also lead to misunderstandings and tensions when different cultural narratives clash. The question then is how we can harness this cultural diversity to enhance peace and integrity in the Nigerian nation. This is the focus of the study.

Research questions

To guide the study, answers were provided to the following questions:

1. What is culture and what are its elements?
2. What are the modes of acquiring culture?
3. What is the cultural heritage among the ethnic groups in Nigeria and how can they be harnessed to enhance peace and integrity in Nigeria?

Understanding the concept of culture

The etymological analysis of the term ‘culture’ is generally perceived to be straightforward and uncontested. According to Saaida (2023), culture is a complex and dynamic concept that includes both tangible elements such as artifacts, tools, and cuisine, reflecting a society’s creativity and traditions and intangible elements encompassing beliefs, values, rituals, stories and ceremonies which are crucial for moral frameworks and social cohesion. Culture according to Louise (2021), is an expansive term that encompasses every aspect of our lives, including people’s behaviours, philosophies, ethics, morals, manners, customs, and traditions. It also covers people’s religious, political, economic, and other activities. Culture includes everything that humans have acquired throughout their individual and social existence. It comprises structured patterns of thinking, feeling, and reacting, primarily acquired and communicated through symbols. These patterns represent the unique accomplishments of human groups, often reflected in their artifacts. The essential core of culture lies in traditional ideas, which have been historically shaped and selected, along with the values associated with them. Culture is the total way of life of a group of people.

Elements of culture

Ideas and symbols are two identified essential components of a culture. Adeniran (2023) asserts that ideas known as non-material culture comprise of values, beliefs, symbols and language that define a society or group while symbols are material culture that includes all the society's physical objects like tools, technology, clothing, eating utensils, and means of transportation. In essence, material culture pertains to the tangible objects and possessions of a group, while nonmaterial culture encompasses the ideas, attitudes, and beliefs of a society. Both material and non-material elements of culture are interconnected, with physical items frequently representing cultural concepts (Kaur & Kaur, 2016). Among the cognitive elements, beliefs, values, language and symbols which are identified as main elements of culture, language is chiefly recognized because it significantly influences how individuals make sense of life and connect with others. In the light of Saaida (2023), language plays a vital role in culture, serving as a tool for communication, carrying spreading cultural knowledge, and shaping identities, for communicating thought patterns, and perspectives across individuals and communities. In a similar analysis, Okafor et al. (2018) state that language embodies a distinctive human trait, representing a unique characteristic of human identity and the invaluable marker of superiority within the broader context of culture. It serves not only as a tool for social interaction but also as an essential aspect of human existence. However, language serves as the gateway to culture, acting as a vehicle that enables groups to engage in their intricate social interactions. It imparts cultural heritage and fosters a sense of identity within a culture. Language plays a significant role in the development of both material and non-material aspects of culture.

Modes of acquiring culture

The acquisition of culture is fundamentally an intellectual process. The material aspects of culture gain significance primarily through the mind. This characteristic enables individuals to understand and learn about their cultural surroundings. According to Mahadi and Jafari (2021), culture is acquired through interactions with others, making it a social product rather than something natural, innate, or automatic. Key factors in this transmission include the dissemination of information and knowledge within a society, social changes, interpersonal relationships, and mass media. As a result, culture is passed down from generation to generation, with its elements being transferred between locations, fragmented into various subcultures, and ultimately subject to crises. Most anthropological findings demonstrate that a significant portion of culture is learned unconsciously by being exposed to the language, opinions, and behaviours of others. As people continue to learn throughout their lives, they are always absorbing aspects of their cultures. Furthermore, people may adopt elements from cultures different from their own, especially if they have the chance to live in a different cultural setting or interact frequently with individuals from another culture. These anthropological observations are embedded in enculturation, acculturation and transculturation (Dhall, 2023). For Saaida (2023), culture can be learned or acquired through imitation whereby an individual observes and replicates others behaviour (this allows for the transfer of information between individuals and down generation without the need for genetic inheritance). Culture is also acquired through indoctrination, involving the process of deliberately inculcating ideas, attitudes, cognitive strategies or a professional methodology. Socialization including talking or understanding other people to establish a relationship could also disseminate culture. However, culture is also transmitted from one generation to the next through learning and is reflected in various aspects of life, including literature, religion, music, clothing, cooking, and daily activities (Asikaogu, 2018).

Cultural practices among ethnic groups in Nigeria

Cultural narratives among the major ethnic groups of Nigeria are summed up in their unique valued arts, customs, festivals, sacred or worship practices, norms, values, ideologies, clothing styles, traditional monuments and architecture, technology, and technological sites, along with other artefacts that are treasured and preserved for their cultural significances. Onyima (2016) identifies the Igbo in the East, the Yoruba in the West, and the Hausa-Fulani in the north as the major ethnic groups in Nigeria and these groups hold onto their oral traditions which remain a vital cultural heritage management tool and also hold significance in contemporary Nigeria societies. Clan and village leaders, kings, chiefs, priests, elders, and older men and women act as the keepers of these oral traditions which include proverbs, moonlight tales and dances (called akukoifo/egwuonwa among the Igbo of eastern Nigeria), adages, lullabies, poems, riddles, incantations, praise songs like oriki, and religious recitations such as Ifa verses among the Yoruba of western Nigeria, reflecting the cultural heritage of each community. These Nigerian ethnic groups also practice festival theatre which refers to dramatic activities that take place during festivals. These performances reflect the beliefs, ideas, and customs of every group. Essentially, the festival theatre is a communal drama where people express their religious, secular, and aesthetic philosophies within the festival setting (Ayangaor, 2016).

In a study conducted by Dzeka and Okla (2016) on Hausa-Fulani cultural heritage, it was noted that the earliest form of worship in Hausa land was animism, involving pagan idol worshipping. It was not until the 14th century that Fulani missionaries from Mali began converting people from paganism to Islam. However, the northern population continued blending pagan practices with Islam until the Islamic Jihad of the early 19th century, led by Usman Dan Fodio, which transformed Hausa land into a theocratic state governed by Islamic laws. This shift deeply impacted their social life, including marriage and education, which became strongly influenced by Islamic and Arabic culture. Women were placed in purdah and required to wear veils in public. Hausa architectural styles also adopted Arabic influences. While farming remains the major occupation, the people are also involved in crafts like weaving and dyeing of fabrics. All ethnic groups in the Northern Region have distinct and rich cultures and traditions that set them apart from one another. Despite these cultural differences, a significant portion of people from Northern Nigeria use Hausa as the lingua franca. The Fulani live alongside the Hausa. They are predominantly nomadic and primarily practice Islam, though some follow a syncretic form of worship. In the opinion of Labaran and Ibrahim (2023), the Fulani strictly uphold their traditions and culture wherever they go, adhering to a code of behaviour called ‘pulaaku,’ which emphasizes qualities like shyness, bravery, and cattle ownership. The Fulani community places a high importance on honour and respect, considering these values essential for upholding social order. Consequently, when they perceive a violation of their honour, they may respond with violence to seek revenge, which can include involvement in banditry. Fulani basic settlement, known as ‘wuru,’ consists of a man and his dependents. These settlements are social but temporary, as they do not include women and primarily serve as shelters for the nomadic herders tending their cattle. Households among the Fulani are patrilocal and can range from a single nuclear family to over a hundred people. Families typically stay in wet-season camps, while younger males or hired non-Fulani herders accompany the cattle to dry-season camps. In terms of crafts, the Fulani are primarily known for leatherworks, while many former slaves, who have adopted Fulani ethnicity, engage in West African crafts such as silversmithing, goldsmithing, ironworking, and basket making. There is a division of labour: cattle herding is a male activity, while tending and milking cattle are done by women, who may

also sell dairy products. It is common to see women gracefully carrying milk or cheese in northern Nigerian towns. Adolescent males traditionally manage herd movement, while elders handle political decisions and negotiate with farmers for safe passage of their herds (Shaguy, 2023).

Varvar and Akor (2016) conducted a study on Yoruba culture. In their perspective, the Yoruba people are known for being deeply religious and showing great respect for superiors and elders. The Oni of Ife is considered the spiritual leader of all Yoruba. They traditionally live in large towns (such as Ile-ife , Oyo, Ibadan, Ogbomosho, Oshogbo, Ilorin, Abeokuta, Ilesha, and Ede) making them the most urbanized group in Nigeria. The growth of these urban centers stemmed partly from the need for defense and largely from their highly centralized political system. The extended family is the fundamental social unit, with each family having a large compound in the town and farmland in rural areas. According to Adekunle (2021), the Yoruba worship several deities, including Sango (god of thunder), Oya, Ogun, Obatala, Osun etc and celebrate festivals such as the Osun festival, Ogun festival, Egungun festival etc. They are renowned for their craftsmanship, excelling in wood carving, bronze working, and iron smelting. The famous terracotta and bronze heads of Ife, notable in Nigerian cultural history, were created by the Yorubas. Their rich culture is expressed through various dances, rituals, and myths. Due to the forest vegetation in this region, the primary occupations of the people include fishing and the cultivation of root crops, as well as trees such as rubber, cocoa, and kola nuts. They also grow tobacco on a large scale for commercial purposes. Before the discovery of crude oil, cocoa and palm products were the main cash crops exported from Nigeria. The people in this area take pride in their beautiful attire, including Aso-Oke, Ofi, Aran, and Agbada. Dress is gender-specific; the common outfit consists of a trouser (Sokoto) paired with a jumper or broad shirt for men and a blouse for women. Men wear Buba, Esiki, and Sapara as undergarments, while Dandogo, Agbada, Gbarye, Sulia, and Oyala serve as outer garments. Women wear Iro, Buba, and Gele, with Tobi and Sinmi as their undergarments (Adejumo, 2021).

The Igbo people have a rich culture that is still actively practiced. They believe in a Supreme Being and worship various deities, with Amadioha (god of thunder) being the most prominent. Igbo families live in dispersed compounds, each typically featuring a shrine for worship. Igbo culture is also reflected in their artistic practices, such as blacksmithing and the creation of human and animal figures through bronze or aluminum casting. The Igbo hold various festivals that re-enact historical experiences, including the Masquerade and Ofala festivals. Significant cultural artifacts, like those discovered at Igbo-Ukwu during well digging, highlight their heritage. Elders, often serving as ritualists, medicine men, and diviners, act as the custodians of Igbo traditions and cultural values (Asikaogu, 2018).

What appears today as Igbo cultural identity according to Ohadike (2017), is a product of 20th century movement. Prior to the event, Igbo language is perceived as composing of numerous dialects due to village separations by thick vegetation. With the colonial era (1900-1960), many Igbo individuals moved away from their hometowns to settle in urban areas, workplaces, and institutions of higher education leading to the realization that what is being believed to be separate languages were actually various dialects of a single language, and that all Igbo speakers shared a common cultural and sociopolitical framework. Though the truism of Ohadike's (2017) claim remains uncertain, Igbo people are known a with culture encompassing of a wide range of customs, practices, and traditions that blend ancient traditions with contemporary ideas. Primarily, elements of Igbo culture include visual arts, music, dance forms, clothing, and language dialects. One significant cultural event celebrated by the Igbo is the annual New Yam Festival.

Chukwu (2015) in a study identifies compassionate nature as a key aspect of the traditional Igbo culture which permeates their social, political, and economic spheres. Hospitality is deeply ingrained in Igbo culture and has been a significant aspect of Igbo life for centuries. This trait, exhibited both intentionally and unintentionally, was not limited to any specific Igbo group rather it was a common practice within the entire Igbo society. Similarly, Odi et al. (2023) underscore adventure as a part of Igbo cultural heritage. In their view, culture encompasses not only an individual's social behaviour or heritage but also their sense of identity. In essence, the Igbo cultural narratives particularly language is richly adorned with elaborate and instructional proverbs, allowing speakers to convey their messages without causing discomfort to the listeners during discussions. Proverbs go beyond offering advice or expressing universal truths serving as the core around which people live, encapsulate and reflect life experiences (Agbo et al., 2019).

Harnessing Nigerian cultural heritage for peace and security.

This paper identifies that the rich and diverse cultural traditions across the core ethnic groups of Nigeria can play a vital role in bridging communities, fostering mutual understanding, and encouraging peace. Examining the roles of cultures in fostering peace and integrity, Kanika and Amit (2024) submit that culture and socialization are intertwined forces that influence the beliefs, values, and behaviours of people within a society. From birth to death, individuals are embedded in a cultural environment that shapes their understanding of themselves and those around them, affecting their thoughts, actions, and interactions. Through socialization, people absorb cultural norms and values, gaining the knowledge and skills needed to navigate the complexities of life. Generally, culture not only fosters a sense of identity and belonging but also acts as a guide for appropriate conduct in specific social settings. Hence, communal life is made possible because community members share a set of meanings that allow them to make coherent sense of the world. This shared understanding forms the group's common sense, which underpins all communication and organized activities. Hence, cultural elements including language are instrumental in teaching core cultural moral values and peacebuilding.

Traditional dances and music, which unite people, along with communal values and customs that promote mutual respect, have been essential in fostering peaceful coexistence among diverse ethnic groups of Nigeria. Drawing from the general African cultural perspectives, Musya (2024) asserts that traditional African values, beliefs, and practices have been instrumental in promoting peace and unity across the continent. A central value in many African cultures is the concept of "Ubuntu", which highlights the interconnectedness and mutual dependence of individuals and communities. This philosophy fosters a sense of collective responsibility for the welfare of everyone and encourages cooperation to address issues and maintain social harmony. However, Nigerian cultural practices like music, dance, and storytelling are vital in promoting peace and unity. They serve as vehicles for conveying cultural values, history, and social messages, often bringing people from different backgrounds together to celebrate shared cultural experiences. Moreover, traditional religious practices, (such as ancestor veneration), foster a sense of connection to ancestral heritage, acting as a unifying force across ethnic groups in Nigeria. There are other traditional Nigerian practices that can enhance peace and unity across the continent. One such practice is communal work which involves community members collaborating on a shared project, like building a school or community center. This practice fosters a sense of collective responsibility and ownership of community resources, promoting cooperation and unity.

The use of traditional justice systems could support peace, unity and integrity in Nigeria. Many Nigerian ethnic groups utilize systems like village councils and tribal courts to resolve conflicts and encourage reconciliation. These systems often emphasize restoring relationships and healing social rifts rather than imposing punitive measures, thereby contributing to social harmony and unity. In the opinion of Akoh et al. (2022), the lifestyle of an ethnic group is reflected in their daily routines and interactions. Traditional Nigerian societies historically adhered to codes of conduct that shaped their way of life. Breaching these norms incurred sanctions, as they were integral to the oral narratives that transmitted cultural ethos from generation to generation. This underscores the oral narrative's role in advocating for peace and security, as societal harmony begins within its smallest units. The functional artistry of oral traditions encompasses communication, teaching, and social commentary, positioning it as a tool for peace-building. Peace, essential for national development, hinges significantly on the language used, connecting harmonious relationships with spoken words. Oral narratives not only facilitate communication but also support and sustain peace, which foster societal unity and collaboration for collective well-being. Culture brings beauty in our lives through the Arts and makes us aesthetic beings; and it is culture that makes us ethical beings by bringing us closer to other human beings and teaching us the values of love, tolerance, integrity and peace. Therefore, all the elements of our culture if properly harnessed could re-fetch us the eluded peace and integrity. Nigerians have been dangerously weaned away from their culture. A practical re-trace and re-link to our cultural heritage is the best way to enhance peace and integrity.

Conclusion

Every individual is part of a unique group, reflecting their distinct thoughts and culture. It is simple to categorize them within their group and differentiate them from others. Hence, culture forms the heart of society, essential for its existence. It distinguishes humans from animals, being a heritage passed down through generations. Culture encompasses customs, behaviours, and traditions, constituting the complete way of life for a community. Cultural narratives are cultural heritage encompassing all the aspects and values of culture passed down from ancestors to off springs across generations. These elements if valued, safeguarded, and preserved with continuous tradition, and vehemently transmitted, will instill sense of pride, peace and integrity to those who share them.

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